

LOCALIZATION AND TRACKING OF GOLD NANOPARTICLES USING MMWAVE FMCW RADAR

Yonathan Eder^{*1}, Ravit Abel^{*2,3}, Avi Schroeder², and Yonina C. Eldar¹

¹Faculty of Math and Computer Science, Weizmann Institute of Science, Israel

²Department of Chemical Engineering, Technion, Haifa, Israel

³ The Norman Seiden Multidisciplinary Program for Nanoscience and Nanotechnology, Technion, Haifa, Israel

ABSTRACT

Gold nanoparticles (GNPs) hold promise to improve the detection and treatment of diseases, such as cancer and Alzheimer's. However, the detection of GNPs in the body remains an unmet technological challenge. This work introduces a new methodology for remotely localizing and tracking GNPs in various therapeutic settings, including through biological tissues, using a compact millimeter-wave radar system. By appropriately modeling the problem, we propose a method that localizes GNP concentrations as well as high sensitivity for detecting changes in concentrations that relate to changes in the intensity of the reflected signals. Our approach paves the way to a first-ever noninvasive, non-ionizing, simple approach for bioimaging and tracking of GNP inside the body.

Index Terms— Bioimaging, frequency modulated continuous wave radar, gold nanoparticles, millimeter-wave, single-input-multiple-output.

1. INTRODUCTION

Bioimaging is a powerful medical tool, allowing tissue visualization and diagnosis, and is crucial for providing effective medical treatment. Gold nanoparticles (GNPs) are promising compounds for bioimaging and theranostics due to their unique physical and chemical properties and tendency to react with electromagnetic radiation [1–4]. In addition, GNPs are biocompatible and FDA-approved compounds, serving as contrast agents, conjugated markers, and therapeutic components [5–8]. GNPs as bioimaging contrast agents allow visualization improvement, disease phenotyping, and imaging-guided drug therapy. Due to their tendency to accumulate in tumors and ability to bind to specific receptors via conjugated linkers, GNPs can be used to identify and study target structures of tumors and metastases. [9–12].

Currently, they are scanned by imaging techniques such as magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), computed tomography (CT), and positron emission tomography (PET) [13–15]. However, the latter are costly and require large, complicated equipment as well as trained medical staff for operation [1]. They may cause discomfort to patients due to the physical constraints of prolonged scanning and

Fig. 1: Illustration of the proposed approach for localizing and tracking GNP concentrations inside a brain tissue using mmWave radar and an adequate algorithm. Created with BioRender.com

contain risks of ionizing radiation in CT and PET, and of magnetic fields in MRI. These limitations mean that patients may be misdiagnosed, or mistreated and that long-term monitoring is less accessible.

Millimeter-wave (mmWave) frequency-modulated-continuous-wave (FMCW) radars have recently gained a lot of interest in the autonomous vehicles sector [16–18] and health care, demonstrating vital sign monitoring, sleeping monitoring, and cardiovascular disease diagnosis [19–25]. Due to their feasibility in terms of miniaturization, cost, and infrastructure as well as their unique properties allowing high-resolution remote sensing and spatial separation of objects, even in cluttered environments with proper signal processing [19–22]. Several works used the well-known *angle-FFT* technique to spatially localize objects with a mmWave FMCW radar [17–20]. This procedure converts the radar data into range-azimuth planes using 1-D FFTs along the ADC samples axis followed by 1-D FFTs over the receiver elements axis. However, this approach is heavily influenced by reflections from static objects in the radar's field of view (FOV) and exhibits relatively poor angular resolution due to FFT processing limitations [17], making it unsuitable for high-resolution localization and tracking of GNPs.

In this work, we propose a method that for the first time employs a low-cost off-the-shelf mmWave radar to remotely localize and track clusters of GNPs in various scenarios. We develop a mathematical signal model using single-input-multiple-output (SIMO) FMCW radar. Based on this model, we extract range-angle maps that allow accurate localization and tracking of GNP concentrations with high sensitivity. The proposed methodology was evaluated for several concentrations in different setups, including *ex-vivo* brain tissue, as illustrated in Fig. 1. This approach paves the way toward a simple, non-invasive, and non-ionizing method for bioimaging and spatiotemporal tracking of GNPs.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, we

^{*}The authors contributed equally. This research was supported by the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program (grant No. 101000967), and ERC Smart Nanoparticles (grant No. 101089009), by the Israel Science Foundation (grant No. 536/22, 1881/21), by the Manya Igel Centre for Biomedical Engineering and Signal Processing and partially supported by the Israeli Council for Higher Education (CHE) via the Weizmann Data Science Research Center. The authors acknowledge the support of the Ministry of Science and Technology, Israel (3-17418), the Louis Family Cancer Research Fund, and Levinson Family Recruitment Foundation. R.A acknowledges the "The Leonard and Diane Sherman foundation".

propose a model for localizing and tracking GNPs using a SIMO FMCW radar. Based on this model, we develop the proposed methodology in Section 3. In Section 4, we provide experimental results and analysis. Section 5 concludes the work.

2. SIMO FMCW SIGNAL MODEL

Suppose a linear FMCW radar transmits L frames of *chirp* signals [29] toward a solution containing a GNP concentration, regarded as an object at a distance d_0 and azimuth angle θ_0 relative to the radar antennas. The reflected echo signals are mixed with the transmitted ones and sampled by an ADC, yielding discrete base-band (*beat*) signals [30, 31] with attenuated amplitude x_0 corresponding to the radar-cross-section (RCS) of the measured GNPs. The FMCW radar is based on a SIMO Uniform Linear Array (ULA) with a single transmitter and K receivers located at $r_k \triangleq (k-1)\lambda/2$, for $k = 1, \dots, K$, where λ is the *chirp*'s maximal wavelength. Ideally, to measure a single object at angle θ_0 and distance d_0 (here, the GNP concentration), one can employ the standard signal model based on [19]:

$$y[n, k, l] = x_0 e^{j(2\pi f_0 n T_f + \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} r_k \sin \theta_0 + \psi_0[l])} \quad (1)$$

for $n = 1, \dots, N$ *fast-time* samples, $k = 1, \dots, K$ receivers, and $l = 1, \dots, L$ *slow-time* frames. T_f denotes the ADC sampling interval and f_0 is the *beat* frequency which satisfies $f_0 \triangleq \frac{2S}{c} d_0$ where c denotes the speed of light and $S \triangleq B/T_c$ is the rate of the frequency sweep of each *chirp*, with B and T_c respectively being the *chirp*'s total bandwidth and duration. Since we are measuring static aggregates of GNPs, changes in motion along the *slow-time* axis l are negligible; thus $\psi_0[l]$ is considered as phase noise. We note that the received amplitude, distance and angle $\{x_0, d_0, \theta_0\}$ are unknown in advance.

However, in realistic indoor environments, the received signal is affected by background noise as well as reflections from clutter in varying angular and radial positions. Hence, the extended model for a general case of $Q > 1$ objects in the radar's FOV is given by

$$y[n, k, l] = \sum_{q=1}^Q x_q e^{j(2\pi f_q n T_f + \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} r_k \sin \theta_q + \psi_q[l])} + w[n, k, l], \quad (2)$$

where $\{w[n, l, k]\}$ is a 3-D sequence of zero mean i.i.d. complex Gaussian noise with variance σ^2 . The received signal is comprised of Q components where the q 'th component is defined by four parameters: a constant amplitude x_q , related to the RCS of the q 'th object, a *beat* frequency f_q which is proportional to the q 'th object's radial distance d_q by $f_q \triangleq \frac{2S}{c} d_q$, an azimuth angle θ_q and a phase noise $\psi_q[l]$.

Assuming that each object has a distinct pair of distance and angle, we can rewrite the model in (2) for M general radial distances $\{d_m\}_{m=1}^M$ and P general azimuth angles $\{\theta_p\}_{p=1}^P$ as follows

$$y[n, k, l] = \sum_{p=1}^P \sum_{m=1}^M x_{m,p} e^{j(2\pi f_m n T_f + \phi_p[k] + \psi_{m,p}[l])} + w[n, k, l], \quad (3)$$

where each $\{m, p\}$ component is associated with reflection from a different pair of distance and angle, including reflection from the GNP concentration, as the component in (1). Based on the latter, $x_{m,p}$ denotes the *beat* amplitude of the $\{m, p\}$ 'th component, which can be zero if there is no reflection and includes the unknown amplitude of the GNP concentration, x_0 . Each *beat* frequency f_m is distinct and proportional to a different radial distance from the radar d_m :

$$f_m \triangleq \frac{2S}{c} d_m, \quad m = 1, \dots, M \leq N. \quad (4)$$

where the unknown distance d_0 is among the distances $\{d_m\}_{m=1}^M$. The azimuth angles $\{\theta_p\}_{p=1}^P$ are reflected in the following phase shifts due to the ULA antenna geometry:

$$\phi_p[k] = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} r_k \sin \theta_p, \quad k = 1, \dots, K \leq P, \quad (5)$$

where the unknown angle θ_0 is among the angles $\{\theta_p\}_{p=1}^P$. Lastly, $\psi_{m,p}[l]$ is the phase noise of the $\{m, p\}$ 'th component.

By defining the *slow-time* varying complex amplitude

$$\tilde{x}_{m,p}[l] \triangleq x_{m,p} e^{j\psi_{m,p}[l]}, \quad l = 1, \dots, L, \quad (6)$$

for each frame l we can assemble the samples of $y[n, k, l]$ from (3) into the matrix $\mathbf{Y}_l \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times K}$. This leads to the model

$$\mathbf{Y}_l = \mathbf{A} \mathbf{X}_l \mathbf{B} + \mathbf{W}_l, \quad l = 1, \dots, L, \quad (7)$$

where $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times M}$ is a Vandermonde matrix, whose entries are given by $\mathbf{A}(n, m) \triangleq \exp(j2\pi f_m n T_f)$, $\mathbf{B} \in \mathbb{C}^{P \times K}$ whose entries are given by $\mathbf{B}(p, k) \triangleq e^{j\phi_p[k]}$. $\mathbf{X}_l \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times P}$ is the unknown matrix of complex amplitudes which satisfy $\mathbf{X}_l(m, p) \triangleq \tilde{x}_{m,p}[l]$ (6), and $\mathbf{W}_l \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times K}$ is the noise matrix where $\mathbf{W}_l(n, k) \triangleq w[n, k, l]$.

To examine the effect of varying GNP concentrations on the parameters $\{x_0, d_0, \theta_0\}$, we perform U independent trials as a function of concentration. In each trial, L frames of *chirps* are transmitted toward a known GNP concentration. Hence, we make the following assumptions for every trial $u = 1, \dots, U$:

- A-1 The parameters $\{x_0, d_0, \theta_0\}$ are constant in all L frames.
- A-2 The number of components $Q \ll MP$. This means that each $\mathbf{X}_l, l = 1, \dots, L$ is a Q -sparse matrix.
- A-3 The GNP reflection is the strongest among all other objects in the radar's FOV.

Based on the model in (7), the goal is to estimate the triplet $\{x_0^{(u)}, d_0^{(u)}, \theta_0^{(u)}\}$ for $u = 1, \dots, U$ trials, and by thus track their values for varying GNP concentrations.

3. LOCALIZATION AND TRACKING OF GNPS

Our solution starts with preliminary processing to assemble the matrices \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} (7) based on predefined frequency and angle grids. Then, we describe our approach for estimating $\{x_0^{(u)}, d_0^{(u)}, \theta_0^{(u)}\}_{u=1}^U$.

3.1. Preliminary Processing

In each trial u , we first assemble the radar 3-D data according to the model in (7). Next, we set the dictionary matrix \mathbf{A} by assuming that the distance-related frequencies $\{f_m\}_{m=1}^M$ (4) lie on the Nyquist grid, i.e.,

$$f_m = \frac{f_{\text{ADC}}}{N} i_m, \quad i_m = 0, \dots, M-1, \quad (8)$$

where $f_{\text{ADC}} \triangleq 1/T_f$ is determined by the ADC component. Using (8) and since $\mathbf{A}(n, m) \triangleq e^{j2\pi f_m n T_f}$, we have that $\mathbf{A}(n, m) = e^{j2\pi \frac{i_m}{N} n}$. As for the dictionary matrix \mathbf{B} , the phase shifts $\{\phi_p[k]\}_{k=1}^K$ (5) are set to cover a FOV of 180 degrees according to the following angle grid

$$\theta_p = -90 + i_p \Delta_\theta, \quad i_p = 0, \dots, P-1, \quad P = \frac{180}{\Delta_\theta}, \quad (9)$$

where Δ_θ denotes the spacing of the angle grid. Then, by (5), (9) and since $\mathbf{B}(p, k) \triangleq e^{j\phi_p[k]}$, we get $\mathbf{B}(k, p) = e^{j\pi(k-1) \sin(-90+i_p \Delta_\theta)}$.

3.2. Estimation of Amplitude, Range and Angle

Based on A-1, we start by coherently integrating the measurements $\{\mathbf{Y}_l\}_{l=1}^L$ (7) to increase the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), i.e., we define the average matrix $\bar{\mathbf{Y}} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times K}$ by the element-wise averaging $\bar{\mathbf{Y}} \triangleq \frac{1}{L} \sum_{l=1}^L \mathbf{Y}_l$ which according to (7) satisfies

$$\bar{\mathbf{Y}} = \mathbf{A} \bar{\mathbf{X}} \mathbf{B} + \bar{\mathbf{W}}, \quad (10)$$

where $\bar{\mathbf{X}} \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times P}$: $\bar{\mathbf{X}} \triangleq \frac{1}{L} \sum_{l=1}^L \mathbf{X}_l$ and $\bar{\mathbf{W}} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times K}$: $\bar{\mathbf{W}} \triangleq \frac{1}{L} \sum_{l=1}^L \mathbf{W}_l$. By A-1, A-2 and (10), $\bar{\mathbf{X}}$ is a sparse matrix. Hence, we recover it from $\bar{\mathbf{Y}}$ using the following optimization problem:

$$\hat{\mathbf{X}} = \arg \min_{\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times P}} \|\bar{\mathbf{Y}} - \mathbf{A} \mathbf{X} \mathbf{B}\|_F^2 + \gamma \|\mathbf{X}\|_1 \quad (11)$$

Here, to promote the sparsity in $\bar{\mathbf{X}}$ we use the regularization parameter $\gamma \geq 0$ and the mixed L_1 norm defined as the sum of all absolute values of $\bar{\mathbf{X}}$. Here, we solve (11) using the fast iterative soft-thresholding algorithm (FISTA) [33, 34], and find the support \mathcal{S} by selecting the Q largest magnitudes of $\bar{\mathbf{X}}$. We note that predetermined boundaries of range and angle, which serve as a region of interest (ROI), can aid in evaluating \mathcal{S} , which finds Q pairs of 2D $\{m, p\}$ coordinates. We further note that the magnitudes of $\hat{\mathbf{X}}$ form the range-angle localization map.

Using \mathcal{S} , we estimate the amplitudes of the detected objects by the Least-Squares (LS) solution [32], which by the Vandermonde structure of \mathbf{A} can be written as

$$\hat{x}_{S(q)} = \frac{1}{N} \mathbf{F}_{S(q)} \bar{\mathbf{Y}} \mathbf{B}_{S(q)}^H / \mathbf{B}_{S(q)} \mathbf{B}_{S(q)}^H, \quad q = 1, \dots, Q, \quad (12)$$

where $\mathbf{F}_{S(q)} \in \mathbb{C}^{1 \times N}$ and $\mathbf{B}_{S(q)} \in \mathbb{C}^{1 \times K}$ are respectively the m 'th row of a partial DFT matrix and the p 'th row of \mathbf{B} (7) corresponding to the q 'th element of \mathcal{S} . Finally, based on A-3, we select the estimated amplitude of the GNP by

$$\hat{x}_0 = \max_{q=1, \dots, Q} \{|\hat{x}_{S(q)}|\}. \quad (13)$$

Based on the selected q 'th $\{m, p\}$ pair of \mathcal{S} , the m 'th index corresponds to the estimated radial distance \hat{d}_0 through (4) and (8) while the p 'th index corresponds to the estimated azimuth angle $\hat{\theta}_0$ via (9).

4. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

This section investigates the estimated parameters for several GNP concentrations in various experimental setups and discusses the observed results.

4.1. Experiment Settings

We performed a total of 5 experiments, each comprising $U = 30$ independent trials of 10 seconds, divided into 6 segments of 5 repetitions. In each segment, the transmission was performed towards a different GNP concentration (0.04, 0.2, 1, 5, and 25 [nM]). We used GNPs with a diameter of 5 [nm] purchased from Cytodiagnosics Inc. (Canada) dissolved in double distilled water to mimic GNPs in a biological aqueous environment. In experiments #1 and #2, the radar was placed on a table at a distance of ≈ 20 [cm] horizontally from a 4 [ml] cylindrical glass test vial, as seen in Fig. 2(a). In experiments #3 and #4, we assembled a styrofoam platform in which the radar was placed at a distance of ≈ 35 [cm] beneath a similar glass vial, attached to the upper part of the platform so that vertical

upward transmission is carried out, as seen in Fig. 2(b). To examine the ability to detect GNPs through complex biological tissues, we used an *ex-vivo* cow brain in experiment #5, where the radar was placed on a table at a distance of ≈ 20 [cm] horizontally from a 3 [mm] silicon test tube, inserted into the center of the brain to stimulate a blood vessel, as illustrated in Fig. 2(c). In all the experiments, we directed the radar towards the center of the GNP concentration, i.e., at an azimuth angle of approximately 0 [deg] relative to the radar antennas.

The selected radar system is based on Texas Instruments IWR1443 76 to 81 [GHz] FMCW mm-Wave sensor [29], utilizing its ULA configuration of a single transmitter (Tx0) and $K = 4$ receivers (Rx0-Rx3). The main radar parameters for assembling the samples in (7) were set as follows: $\lambda = 3.89$ [mm], which corresponds to a center frequency of 77 [GHz], $T_c = 57$ [μ s] and $S = 70$ [MHz/ μ s], which corresponds to a bandwidth of $B \approx 4$ [GHz], and $f_{\text{ADC}} = 4$ [MHz], with selected $N = 200$ and $M = N/2 = 100$. Each 10-second trial u consists of $L = 200$ transmission frames of length 50 [ms], with 100 consecutive chirps per frame, coherently summed to increase the SNR. The parameters for solving (11) using FISTA [33, 34] were set to $\gamma = 1e4$, with Lipschitz constant and maximum number of iterations equal to $1e7$ and 1000, respectively. The range and angle search boundaries for evaluating \mathcal{S} were selected as $[0.17 \ 0.5]$ [m] and $[-40 \ 40]$ [deg], respectively. Finally, the angle grid spacing was set to $\Delta_\theta = 1$ (9).

Fig. 2: Experimental setups. (a) Horizontal transmission towards an upright glass test vial. (b) Vertical transmission towards a lying glass test vial, attached to the upper part of a styrofoam platform. (c) Horizontal transmission towards a silicone test tube inserted into the center of an *ex-vivo* cow brain. Illustration created with BioRender.com

4.2. Results

Here we show the estimated variables $\{\hat{x}_0^{(u)}, \hat{d}_0^{(u)}, \hat{\theta}_0^{(u)}\}_{u=1}^U$ from Exp. #2 (of a glass vial), from Exp. #5 (of a cow brain) and a summary bar plot of all 5 experiments. In addition, we depict the range-angle maps by the absolute values of $\hat{\mathbf{X}}$ (11) from Exp. #2, for trials of different concentrations to show how the maps change accordingly.

One can observe in figures 3(a), 3(b) (Exp. #2) and 3(d), 3(e) (Exp. #5) that both the range and angle estimates $\{\hat{d}_0^{(u)}, \hat{\theta}_0^{(u)}\}_{u=1}^U$ remain stable across trials and correspond to the position of the GNPs center with negligible changes w.r.t. the resolution limitations: $\theta_{\text{res}} \approx 30$ [deg] for $K = 4$ receiver elements and $d_{\text{res}} \triangleq \frac{c}{2B} = 3.75$ [cm] for a 4 [GHz] bandwidth [17]. Figures 3(c), 3(g) (Exp. #2) 3(f), 3(h) (Exp. #5), and 3(i) (summary of all 5 experiments) track the differences in the values of normalized $\{\hat{x}_0^{(u)}\}_{u=1}^U$ in response to changes in GNP concentrations. The normalization is carried out by dividing $\{\hat{x}_0^{(u)}\}_{u=1}^U$ by the average of the values from the water segment, for measuring the changes w.r.t. the water case. Figures 3(g)-3(i) depict the mean \pm standard deviation of each segment and

a significance testing relative to water by one-way ANOVA and Dunnett test, with p denoting the p -value.

Three distinct phenomena can be seen in figures 3(c), 3(f), 3(g), 3(h) and 3(i). First, a gradual increase in the reflected signal amplitudes (expressed in the values of $\hat{x}_0^{(u)}$) due to an increase in the GNP concentration, for 0.04 – 5 [nM]. Second, at concentrations of 0.04 [nM] and 1, 5 [nM], respectively, the intensity of the reflections was significantly lower and higher than water (with $p < 0.002$ in the summarized analysis 3(i)). This suggests that GNPs at these concentrations may be detected in aqueous environments, found in the human body. Third, at concentrations of 0.2 [nM] and 25 [nM], the strength of the reflections is not significantly distinct from the water case, implying that the difference from water is only evident within a restricted range of concentrations. These results show the potential of the proposed approach for long-term monitoring of the accumulation or decay of GNPs in targeted organs for improved diagnosis and treatment.

Finally, Fig. 4 depict the range-angle maps (by the magnitudes of $\hat{\mathbf{X}}$ (11)) from experiment #2, normalized according to the average of the values from the water segment, of each of the following trials (concentrations): $u = 1, 6, 11, 16, 21, 26$ (0, 0.04, 0.2, 1, 5, 25 [nM]). The red \mathbf{x} marks the selected $\hat{x}[l]$ (??) whose indices indicate the frame's estimated location of the GNP cluster by $\hat{d}[l]$ and $\hat{\theta}[l]$. Changes in the color of the cluster can be seen along figures 4(a)-4(f) that correspond to changes in the intensity of the reflections, as shown in Fig. 3(g). Using these maps, it is possible to track clusters of GNPs in varying concentrations and locations.

Fig. 3: Range, angle, and normalized magnitude estimations vs. GNP concentrations. (a)-(c) and (d)-(f): $\{\hat{d}_0^{(u)}\}_{u=1}^U$, $\{\hat{\theta}_0^{(u)}\}_{u=1}^U$ and normalized $\{\hat{x}_0^{(u)}\}_{u=1}^U$ for experiments #2 (glass vial) and #5 (cow brain), respectively. The dashed red lines and black vertical lines respectively denote the search boundaries and the transitions between different GNP concentrations. (g)-(i): The effect of different GNP concentrations on the normalized $\{\hat{x}_0^{(u)}\}_{u=1}^U$, for experiments #2 (g), #5 (h) and for all 5 experiments (i). Notations for (g)-(i): ns: no significant difference, * : $p < 0.03$, ** : $p < 0.02$, *** : $p < 0.002$, **** : $p < 0.0001$, calculated by one-way ANOVA and Dunnett test.

Fig. 4: Normalized range-angle maps by the absolute values of $\hat{\mathbf{X}}_l$ (??) for $l = 1$ of each of the following trials (concentrations in [nM]): (a) $u = 1$ (0). (b) $u = 6$ (0.04). (c) $u = 11$ (0.2). (d) $u = 16$ (1). (e) $u = 21$ (5). (f) $u = 26$ (25). By evaluating $\{\hat{\mathbf{X}}_l\}_{l=1}^L$, it is possible to localize and track clusters of GNPs in varying concentrations.

5. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we propose a model and method for localizing and tracking a GNP cluster in varying concentrations using mmWave FMCW radar for biological imaging. Based on the suggested model, our approach produces clear range-angle maps for accurate localization and monitoring of the strength of the reflected signals. We found promising results that could pave the way for future bioimaging and medical applications that combine the capabilities of radar with nanotechnology.

6. REFERENCES

- [1] J. Wallyn, N. Anton, S. Akram, and T. F. Vandamme, "Biomedical Imaging: Principles, Technologies, Clinical Aspects, Contrast Agents, Limitations and Future Trends in Nanomedicines," *Pharmaceutical Research*, vol. 36, pp. 1–31, 2019.
- [2] H. P. Lee and A. K. Gaharwar, "Light-Responsive Inorganic Biomaterials for Biomedical Applications," *Advanced Science*, vol. 7, no. 17, pp. 2000863, 2020.
- [3] C. Jiang et al., "Microwave Absorption Properties of Gold Nanoparticle Doped Polymers," *Solid-State Electronics*, vol. 57, no. 1, pp. 19–22, 2011.
- [4] N. Perets et al., "Golden Exosomes Selectively Target Brain Pathologies in Neurodegenerative and Neurodevelopmental Disorders," *Nano Letters*, vol. 19, no. 6, pp. 3422–3431, 2019.
- [5] M. J. Mitchell, M. M. Billingsley, R. M. Haley, M. E. Wechsler, N. A. Peppas, and R. Langer, "Engineering precision nanoparticles for drug delivery," *Nature Reviews Drug Discovery*, vol. 20, no. 2, pp. 101–124, 2021.
- [6] M. I. Anik, N. Mahmud, A. Al Masud, and M. Hasan, "Gold nanoparticles (GNPs) in biomedical and clinical applications: A review," *Nano Select*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 792–828, 2022.
- [7] N. Elahi, M. Kamali, and M. H. Baghersad, "Recent biomedical applications of gold nanoparticles: A review," *Talanta*, vol. 184, pp. 537–556, 2018.
- [8] J. C. L. Chow, "Special Issue: Application of Nanomaterials in Biomedical Imaging and Cancer Therapy," *Nanomaterials*, vol. 12, no. 5, pp. 726, 2022.

- [9] E. M. Mettenbrink, W. Yang, and S. Wilhelm, "Bioimaging with Upconversion Nanoparticles," *Advanced Photonics Research*, vol. 3, no. 12, pp. 2200098, 2022.
- [10] J. C. Hsu, Z. Tang, O. E. Eremina, M. A. Sofias, T. Lammers, J. F. Lovell, C. Zavaleta, W. Cai and D.P. Cormode, "Nanomaterial-based contrast agents," *Nature Reviews Methods Primers*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 30, 2023.
- [11] M. Bouché, J. C. Hsu, Y. C. Dong, J. Kim, K. Taing, and D. P. Cormode, "Recent Advances in Molecular Imaging with Gold Nanoparticles," *Bioconjugate Chemistry*, vol. 31, no. 2, pp. 303-314, 2020.
- [12] S. Siddique and J. C. L. Chow, "Application of Nanomaterials in Biomedical Imaging and Cancer Therapy," *Nanomaterials*, vol. 10, no. 9, p. 1700, 2020.
- [13] D. Maccora et al., "Gold Nanoparticles and Nanorods in Nuclear Medicine: A Mini Review," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 9, no. 16, pp. 3232, 2019.
- [14] C. de la Encarnación, D. Jimenez de Aberasturi, and L. M. Liz-Marzán, "Multifunctional plasmonic-magnetic nanoparticles for bioimaging and hyperthermia," *Advanced Drug Delivery Reviews*, vol. 189, pp. 114484, 2022.
- [15] P. Morris, "Biomedical Imaging: Applications and Advances," Elsevier, 2014.
- [16] K. Yoneda, N. Hashimoto, R. Yanase, M. Aldibaja and N. Suganuma, "Vehicle Localization using 76GHz Omnidirectional Millimeter-Wave Radar for Winter Automated Driving," *2018 IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symposium (IV)*, pp. 971-977, 2018.
- [17] X. Gao, G. Xing, S. Roy, and H. Liu, "Experiments with mmWave Automotive Radar Test-bed," *2019 53rd Asilomar Conference on Signals, Systems, and Computers*, pp. 1-6, 2019.
- [18] X. Gao, S. Roy and G. Xing, "MIMO-SAR: A Hierarchical High-Resolution Imaging Algorithm for mmWave FMCW Radar in Autonomous Driving," *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, vol. 70, no. 8, pp. 7322-7334, 2021.
- [19] A. Ahmad, J. Roh, D. Wang, and A. Dubey, "Vital signs monitoring of multiple people using a FMCW millimeter-wave sensor," *2018 IEEE Radar Conference (RadarConf18)*, pp. 1450-1455, 2018.
- [20] K. Han, and S. Hong, "Detection and Localization of Multiple Humans Based on Curve Length of I/Q Signal Trajectory Using MIMO FMCW Radar," *IEEE Microwave and Wireless Components Letters*, vol. 31, no. 4, pp. 413-416, 2021.
- [21] Y. Eder, and Y. C. Eldar, "Sparsity-Based Multi-Person Non-Contact Vital Signs Monitoring Via FMCW Radar," *IEEE Journal of Biomedical and Health Informatics*, vol. 27, no. 6, pp. 2806-2817, 2023.
- [22] Y. Eder, Z. Liu, and Y. C. Eldar, "Sparse Non-Contact Multiple People Localization and Vital Signs Monitoring Via FMCW Radar," *2023 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP)*, pp. 1-5, 2023.
- [23] F. Fioranelli, J. Le Kerneec and S. A. Shah, "Radar for Health Care: Recognizing Human Activities and Monitoring Vital Signs," *IEEE Potentials*, vol. 38, no. 4, pp. 16-23, 2019.
- [24] P. Jena and K. N. Sahu, "Millimeter Wave FMCW Radar for Contactless Diagnosis of Cardiovascular Diseases," *2021 2nd International Conference on Range Technology (ICORT)*, pp. 1-6, 2021.
- [25] P. Wang et al., "Research Progress in Millimeter Wave Radar-Based non-contact Sleep Monitoring - A Review," *2021 13th International Symposium on Antennas, Propagation and EM Theory (ISAPE)*, pp. 1-3, 2021.
- [26] U. Rossman, R. Tenne, O. Solomon, I. Kaplan-Ashiri, T. Dardosh, Y. C. Eldar, and, D. Oron, "Rapid quantum image scanning microscopy by joint sparse reconstruction," *Optica*, vol. 6, no. 10, pp. 1290-1296, 2019.
- [27] Y. C. Eldar, *Sampling Theory: Beyond Bandlimited Systems*, U.K., Cambridge Univ. Press, 2015.
- [28] Y. C. Eldar, and G. Kutyniok *Compressed Sensing: Theory and Applications*, U.K., Cambridge Univ. Press, 2012.
- [29] IWR1443 Single-Chip 76- to 81-GHz mmWave Sensor. Available: <https://www.ti.com/document-viewer/IWR1443/datasheet>.
- [30] M. Alizadeh, G. Shaker, J. De Almeida, P. Morita, and S. Safavi-Naeini, "Remote Monitoring of Human Vital Signs Using mm-Wave FMCW Radar," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 54958-54968, 2019.
- [31] E. Turppa, J. Kortelainen, O. Antropov, and T. Kiuru, "Vital Sign Monitoring Using FMCW Radar in Various Sleeping Scenarios," *Sensors*, vol. 20, no. 22, pp. 6505, 2020.
- [32] D. Ruppert, and M. P. Wand, "Multivariate locally weighted least squares regression," *The Annals of Statistics*, pp. 1346-1370, 1994.
- [33] A. Beck, and M. Teboulle, "A Fast Iterative Shrinkage-Thresholding Algorithm for Linear Inverse Problems," *SIAM Journal on Imaging Sciences*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 183-202, 2009.
- [34] D. P. Palomar, and Y. C. Eldar, *Convex Optimization in Signal Processing and Communications*, Cambridge Univ. Press, 2010.